

The Effect of Reward and Punishment to Performance of Driver Grabcar in Depok

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ABSTRACT

The development of business in the era of globalization such as today resulted in higher levels of business competition, no exception in the service sector so that the company must implement a human resource management strategy well for the sake of the company survival and progress. As for the problem in this research is "is the Reward and Punishment affect the performance of Driver GrabCar in the region of Depok Java-West? The objectives in this study are to influence the impact of each variable, Reward (X1) and Punishment (X2) against performance (Y). The population in this study is all Driver GrabCar Partners in Depok Java – West area which amounted to 85 people. Samples were taken amounting to 85 respondents. Then analysis of the data obtained in the form of statistical analysis. Statistical analyses include validity and reliability tests, classical assumption tests, hypothesis tests via F test and T test and coefficient of determination (R²) analysis. The data analysis technique used is a double linear regression analysis that serves to prove the research hypothesis. Data that has fulfilled the validity test, reliability test, and classic assumption test are processed resulting in the following multiple linear regression equations: $Y = 0.418 + 0.087 X1 + 0.166 X2$ Results of analysis can be noted that the value of Kostanta 0.418 The reward regression coefficient (X1) of 0.087 and Punishment (X2) of 0.166 means positive impact on the employee's performance. Therefore, if Reward and Punishment are adjusted to 1 percent, there will be a performance increase (Y) of 0.87 percent. Variable Reward, Punishment and motivation have a positive value and significantly affect the performance of Driver GrabCar in Depok Java-West region. And the

Free the (X1, X2) simultaneously affects the bound variable (Y) of the company. The Adjusted R Square number of 0.690 showed that 69 percent of performance variations could be described by the two independent variables used in regression equation. The remaining 32.2 percent is explained by other variables outside the sentence variable used in this study.

Keywords: reward, punishment, performance, driver grabcar.

INTRODUCTION

Man is God's most perfect creature in the world. People have thought analysis, and creativity to plan, organize, actualize, and control everything in accordance with its functions in management. Because all activities of the company will involve the actions of human resources that exist there. The success of a company is influenced by individual performance of employees; a company will strive to improve the performance of its employees with the expectation of the company's objectives. Given the importance of human resources that include the role, management, and utilization of employees needed to spur employee morale, the company must meet several criteria through the application of resource management concepts and techniques appropriate human beings.

The rapid development of Internet technology provides social change by utilizing the development of information technology, one of which is the emergence of application-based service provider business. One of them is the emergence of

online-based transportation mode that turned out to provide solutions and answer various worries about public transport services. Congestion and fear with public transport security is answered by the presence of online transport applications that provide convenience and comfort for its users. Many companies that offer the same variety of services make competition increasingly stringent.

The online transportation business that is now very well known is Grab at PT. Transportation Solutions Indonesia which has become one of the largest online transportation service provider based in Indonesia, transportation company Based on this application proved to provide significant changes especially for social life. Every company must have the vision, mission, and objectives to be achieved, in a company usually along with developments, the problems experienced by the company are increasingly complex because the company will face more changes and progress Information technology in the era of globalization, the company is also required to be able to achieve the expected target through improving the quality of human resources services. The maximum quality of human resources service to consumers is indispensable in maintaining and improving the quality of the company. To survive and win in the business of service providers based on online applications demanded good performance and quality in the service to consumers from all resources owned by the company, especially human resources as Employees are valuable assets. Human resources have a very strategic position in the organization, meaning that the human element plays an important role in conducting activities to achieve the objectives. For that reason the human resource extensions in the organization are very strong.

According to Jacqueline (2011) in Indah (2017:3541) Employee performance is very important in human resource management. Human resources are one of the factors that determine the success of the

company; hence the performance of employees should be improved in order to provide maximum results for the company. The performance of the employees is very important in a company so that it requires the management of human resources that are planned, directed, intensive, effective and efficient. Human Resource Management

Employee performance is expected to be increased to meet the company objectives. Various ways are done by companies in improving employee performance even though the way from one company to another has different companies. Efforts to improve employee Kineja will have an impact on company productivity.

Pratheepkanth (2011) in Kentjana *et al.* (2018:975) state that company is expected to maintain qualified employees and keep them in order to continue to be motivated, one of them by assigning a specific system or strategy to provide a balance between the expected contributions to what given in the form of a particular reward or award. Reward and punishment are one example of awarding employee rewards for satisfactory results. Through the reward and punishment expected employees will be more qualified and responsible with the task given. Reward and punishment are two words that are opposite to each other, but both of them are interconnected.

Reward is as a reward or bonus given because of one's accomplishments.

The application of reward systems or rewards to outstanding employees will motivate employees to further improve their performance in the works. The company must also apply sanctions or punishment to employees who are lazy and neglect to work because it will interfere with the performance of other employees. Punishment is the suffering given or intentionally inflicted by a person after a breach, offence or offence. Sanctions or punishment are the penalties given due to violations against the prevailing. Reward and punishment should be done by the

company with decent and fair to the employees. The company can not give reward and punishment based on likes or dislikes. Unfair rewards and punishment will cause a social jealousy to arise among employees, thus triggering a negative working relationship and certainly impacting employees' performance. Therefore, rewards and punishment are important to increase the motivation of employees to achieve the best achievement. Companies do not need to dictate employees of what to do or decide, because they have influenced actions or decisions that make employees more attentive to the consequences of the actions or decisions they make. Mistakes in applying will result in demotivation and absence of job satisfaction among employees and if this happens it can lead to low performance of both employees and companies.

The quality or performance of employees should always be maintained and improved, one of which is with the application of reward and punishment. Simultaneously that there is a positive and significant influence between reward, punishment and motivation to performance. So in this research researchers want to know the effects arising from the application of reward and punishment to the performance of the driver GrabCar, and authors interested in conducting research proposals with the title: "The Effect of Reward and Punishment to Performance of Driver GrabCar in Depok-West Java".

METHOD

This research uses quantitative methods, the method of research is essentially a scientific way to obtain data with specific purpose and usability. According to Hadi in Bintarti (2015:1) research is an attempt to discover, develop, and test the truthfulness of a knowledge, which is done by using scientific method..

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Performance, Reward, and Punishment

Employees' performance is not merely information for the promotion or

salary setting for the company. However, how companies can motivate employees and develop a plan to improve the deterioration in performance can be avoided. Employee performance needs an assessment with a view to giving employees a good opportunity for their career plan to be seen from strengths and weaknesses, so that the company can set payroll, provide promotion, and can see employee behaviour. Performance assessment is known as performance rating or performance appraisal. According to Mangkunegara (2012:9) in Mariyani and Sariyati (2017:3542) performance is a reflection of his skills and skills in a particular job that will impact the reward of the company. Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out its duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

Rewards come from English that means prizes, rewards, awards or rewards. According to Irmayanti (2013) in Saputra et al. (2017:3) explains that rewards are also called intrinsic rewards that are part of the work itself, such rewards include a sense of completion, achievement, autonomy and growth, meaning the ability to initiate or complete a job project is important to a number of individuals.

Punishment comes from English which means punishment. According to Purwanto (2006:186) in Saputra et al. (2017:4) Punishment is the suffering given or intentionally caused by a person after a breach, offence or offence. Sanctioned or punishment to officers are much sanctioned can be given in the form of reprimand, warning letters, scoring and even termination or termination of employment. A sanctioned or punitive employee usually does not get a bonus on the corresponding month, or cannot even get a promotion opportunity if the mistake is quite heavy. The purpose of a punishment or punishment to an employee is to cause an unpleasant feeling for someone to not make a bad

thing. This show the analysis result of statistic data.

Reliability test

Table 1. Result of Reliability Test

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Reward	,854	10
Punishment	,824	10
Motivation	,815	10
Performance	,852	10

Source: Processed data results SPSS 2019

From the reliability test results there are four outputs of the first being the reward variable (X1), the punishment variable (X2), the motivation variable (X3) and the performance variable (Y). From these outputs can be known reliability value (Cronbach's Alpha) of each variable > 0.60 then code cleared reliable. Multicollinearity Test.

Table 2. Result of Tolerance Test & VIF

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta				Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	,418	,298			1,404	,164		
Reward	,087	,042	,128		2,061	,043		1,001
Punishment	,166	,083	,178		2,011	,048		2,050
Motivation	,682	,089	,681		7,685	,000		2,051

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

Source: Processed data results 2019

According to the table above, it is known that the tolerance value of the independent variable has a value of > 0.10 and a VIF of < 10, which means that the data used in the study does not occur multicollinearity data. It is known that the VIF values of the entire independent variable are reward, punishment and motivation smaller than 10, and the tolerance value is greater than 0.1. Meaning there is no multicollinearity in this regression model.

Test of coefficient of determination (R2)

Table 3 test result determinations (R2)

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,831 ^a	,690	,678	,28270

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivasi, Reward, Punishment

b. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

Source: Processed data results 2019

Based on the results of the table with the help of SPSS version 25 program, it can be noted that the relationship or correlation between Reward (X1), Punishment (X2) and motivation (X) to employee performance (Y) can be seen through the correlation coefficient. The result of a correlation coefficient or R of 0.831, indicating that the relationship between Reward (X1), Punishment (X2) and motivation (X3) towards employee performance (Y) has a strong relationship of 83.1%

The magnitude value of the coefficient of determination (Adjust R2) amounted to 0.678 or 67.8%. This suggests that the reward, punishment and motivation jointly affect 67.8% of the performance, while the remaining 32.2% is influenced by other variables outside of the study Multiple linear regression analysis

Table 4 test results Double linear analysis

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	,418	,298		1,404	,164
Reward	,087	,042	,128	2,061	,043
Punishment	,166	,083	,178	2,011	,048
Motivasi	,682	,089	,681	7,685	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

Source: Processed data results 2019

Hypothesis test Simultan Test (Test F)

Table 5. Result of Test F

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14,403	3	4,801	60,071	,000 ^b
	Residual	6,473	81	,080		
	Total	20,876	84			

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

b. Predictors: (Constant), Motivasi, Reward, Punishment

Source: Processed data results 2019

Based on the table it is known that the fcalculate value of 60.071 and ftable obtained the result of 2.71, meaning Fcalculate > Ftable and obtained a significant yield of 0.000 < 0.05 thereby the reward variable, punishment and motivation together have a significant influence on the

employee's performance so that it can be declared H0 rejected and H1 accepted.

Partial Test (Test T)

Table 6. Result of Test T

Model	Coefficients ^a					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.418	.298		1,404	,164
	Reward	,087	,042	,128	2,061	,043
	Punishment	,166	,083	,178	2,011	,048
	Motivasi	,682	,089	,681	7,685	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

Source: Processed data results2019

Effect of Reward(X1) to Performance(Y) Driver GrabCar

The reliability test results indicate that the Cronbach Alpha value of each construct or variable is greater than 0.60 which means that a questionnaire that is an indicator of that variable is reliability or reliable. It can be seen from the test results that have been done where the coefficients (r) Alpha count the entire variable larger than the required criteria or the role of Tumb of 0.60 is the reward variable (X1) of the Cronbach Alpha value of 0.854, Punishment (X2) amounting to 0.824 and Performance (Y) of 0.852. Multiple linear regression equations are used to predict how high a work performance value is when the reward value changes. Based on the analysis of multiple linear regression acquired Y equation = 0.418 + 0.087 X1. This means that when the reward is increased, the employee's performance also increases.

Based on the calculation of the attached coefficient of determinant, it can be noted that a percentage of independent variables are rewarded and punishment the dependent variable of the employee's performance by 69%. Or variations of the free variables used in the model are able to explain for 69% of the dependent variable variations. While the remaining 31% is influenced by other variables not examined in this model of research. From the results of the analysis showed that the test T for the reward variable obtained the calculated result of 2.061. Meanwhile the value in the

distribution table 5% T table amounted to 1.98969. Then T count > T table and Ha received with a sig T value of 0.043 is smaller than the value of probability 0.05. The result of the calculation shows that the reward positively affects and there is a significant influence on the performance of the driver GrabCar in Depok.

Effect Punishment (X2) to Performance (Y) Driver GrabCar

The reliability test results indicate that the Cronbach Alpha value of each construct or variable is greater than 0.60 which means that a questionnaire that is an indicator of that variable is reliability or reliable. It can be seen from the test results that have been done where the coefficient (r) Alpha count the entire variable larger than the required criteria or the critical value (role of tumb) 0.60 is the reward variable (X1) of the Cronbach Alpha value 0.854, Punishment (X2) 0.824 and Performance (Y) 0.852. Multiple linear regression equations are used to predict how high an employee's performance value is when the punishment value changes. Based on the analysis of multiple linear regression acquired Y equation = 0.418 + 0.166 X2. This means that when the punishment is upgraded, performance also increases.

Based on the calculation of the attached coefficient of determinant, it can be noted that a percentage of independent variables are rewarded and punishment the dependent variable of the employee's performance by 69%. Or variations of the free variables used in the model are able to explain for 69% of the dependent variable variations. While the remaining 31% is influenced by other variables not examined in this model of research. From the analysis results showed that the test T for the variable punishment obtained the result of the calculated T 2.011. Meanwhile the value of 5% t table distribution table is 1.98969. Then T count > T table and Ha received with a sig T value of 0.048 is smaller than the value of probability 0.05. The result of the calculation shows that punishment

positively affects and there is a significant influence on the performance of the driver GrabCar in Depok Java – West.

Effect Reward (X1) and Punishment (X2) to Performance (Y) Driver GrabCar

The reward is important, because with this reward is expected every individual employees want to work hard and enthusiastic to improve employee performance. Leaders should be aware that employees will be able to work hard with hope, fulfilling the needs and desires of their work. With punishment, employees will be more disciplined and thorough and able to perform their job duties, so as to improve performance. People will work hard, it is understandably because of the encouragement that is so high to produce according to the target they set. Thus if this variable is linked together to the performance of the driver it will be obtained a higher impact. Where if the reward is high, good punishment and motivation is always awake, it will improve the performance better anyway.

Multiple linear regression equations are used to predict how high the employee's performance is when the reward and punishment value change. Based on the analysis of multiple linear regression obtained Y equation = $0.418 + 0.087 X1 + 0.166 X2$. This means that when the reward and punishment are upgraded the driver's performance also increases.

Based on the test results the F showed that the simultaneous influence of two independent variables (reward and punishment) to the employee's performance showed positive results. It is shown from the magnitude of the value F count of 60.071 and with a significant rate of 0.000 (less than 0.05%).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of analysis and discussion that has been done in the study impact Reward and Punishment on performance Driver GrabCar in Depok Java-West region, then there are several

conclusions as follows: (1) Based on the results of a double linear regression analysis that has been performed on this research, obtained the following regression equation: $Y = 0.418 + 0.087 X1 + 0.166 X2 + 0.682 (X3)$, (a) The constant value of 0.418 means that if there is no reward or $X1 = 0$, there is no punishment $X2 = 0$, and there is no motivation of $X3 = 0$. Employees' performance is fixed or constant by 0.418. (b) the reward regression coefficient (X1) of 0.087 means the reward positively affects the performance of Driver GrabCar. So if the reward is adjusted 1% there will be a performance increase (Y) of 0.087%. (c) regression coefficient punishment (X2) of 0.166 means punishment influence to the performance of Driver GrabCar. So if the punishment is adjusted by 1%, there will be a performance increase of 0.166%. (2) Based on the results of double linear regression analysis, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between the reward to the employee's performance. In view of the test-t results (partial) in using IBM SPSS 25: There is a value of T count of 2.061 and ttable of 1.98969 where the T count is greater than t table with a significant rate of 0.043 smaller than the probability value 0.05, so that it can be concluded that there is a positive influence between the reward on the performance of Driver GrabCar, the increasing reward given, the more increasing the performance of employees of the company. (3) Based on the results of double linear regression analysis, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between punishment to the employee's performance. In view of the test-t results (partial) in using IBM SPSS 25: There is a value of t count of 2.011 and t table 1.98969 where the t count is greater than t table with a significant rate of 0.048 smaller than the probability value of 0.05, so that it can be concluded that there is a positive influence between the punishment on the performance of Driver GrabCar, the increasing punishment given the increase and the performance of employees to the company. (4) Based on the research results

of double linear regression analysis, there is a simultaneous influence or there is a relationship between the reward and punishment to the performance of the driver GrabCar. In view of Uji-F's results in using IBM SPSS 25: There is a calculate value of 60.071 greater than the F table of 2.71 and the value of F Sig 0.000 is smaller than the value of Probalitas 0.05. So there is a positive influence between the reward and punishment to the performance of Driver GrabCar in Depok-West Java.

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